

Hierarchical YOLO: Detection and Classification in Norwegian Grocery Stores

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Abstract—This work presents an approach to detecting and classifying Norwegian grocery products in densely packed shelf images. It is developed as part of the Norwegian AI Challenge (March 19–22, 2026) and leverages a hierarchical detection strategy that exploits the taxonomic structure of product categories to improve fine-grained recognition under constrained data conditions.

Index Terms—computer vision, object detection, hierarchical classification, contrastive learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The Norwegian AI Challenge (March 19–22, 2026) is a competition designed to develop and reinforce AI competency in Norway. The methodology presented here was developed for the NorgesGruppen Data: Object Detection task, which focuses on detecting and classifying grocery products in densely packed shelf images under realistic deployment constraints.

The dataset comprises 248 annotated shelf images with approximately 22,700 bounding boxes spanning 356 product categories, supplemented by a set of multi-view reference images for 327 products. Annotations follow the COCO format, including bounding boxes, category labels, and product-level metadata such as barcodes and verified labels. The task is characterised by high object density, significant visual similarity across classes, and limited training data, making it a challenging benchmark for fine-grained retail detection. The problem formulation reflects real-world retail scenarios in which models must jointly address detection and identification under constrained data regimes. Effective approaches typically combine robust object detectors with strategies for fine-grained recognition, such as leveraging reference images or embedding-based matching.

Additional constraints were imposed by the competition: submitted models were required to be under 420 MB and to complete inference within a fixed time budget. The research question addressed is therefore how to construct a powerful discriminative model within a constrained deployment environment. To explore this challenge, a Hierarchical Supervised Contrastive learning strategy is deployed.

II. RELATED WORK

Detecting objects in real-world environments requires a system to contend with a range of compounding challenges. Instances may partially occlude one another, appear in unfamiliar spatial configurations, or vary in appearance in ways

that weaken learned feature associations. When training data is limited, these difficulties intensify. The problem becomes harder still when the task carries implicit logical structure, such as the taxonomic relationships between product categories.

A. Dense Object Detection

Goldman et al. [1] introduced SKU-110K alongside a Soft-IoU / EM-Merger approach tailored to densely packed retail scenes, establishing the core detection challenge that this work targets. YOLOv8 [3] provides an efficient anchor-free backbone well-suited to environments such as grocery stores where objects appear in high-density configurations.

B. Hierarchical Classification

Beyond flat detection, product recognition requires respecting taxonomic structure. Tsenkova et al. [2] proposed hY-OLO, attaching per-level classification branches to a YOLOv8 backbone for pre-cropped images. The present work extends that formulation into a full detection pipeline, introducing bidirectional gradient flow and a unified detection training objective. Hierarchical performance is evaluated using the F1Hier metric of Kiritchenko et al. [4].

C. Contrastive Learning

To sharpen feature representations across the hierarchy, this work draws on supervised contrastive learning [5]. The HierSupCon (Hierarchical Supervised Contrastive learning) stage adapts positive and negative sampling to respect product-level relationships, following the spirit of Zhang et al. [6] but applied directly to detection features rather than pre-extracted embeddings.

III. METHODOLOGY

The pipeline begins with pre-training on related data to provide the backbone with knowledge of densely packed shelf scenes, and then fine-tunes the model to perform hierarchical product recognition. This design is motivated by a product taxonomy organised into four levels of increasing specificity. Classifying hundreds of visually similar objects with a flat label space would be an extremely difficult supervised learning problem. By using a taxonomy, the complexity of the task is reduced: once the model determines which shelf section it is observing, the number of candidate classes falls dramatically.

The taxonomy is summarised in Table I.

TABLE I
FOUR-LEVEL PRODUCT TAXONOMY USED FOR HIERARCHICAL CLASSIFICATION.

Level	Description	Classes	Example
L0	Section	4	Hot drinks, breakfast
L1	Format / type	30	Filter coffee, capsules
L2	Brand	149	Nescafé, Friele, Evergood
L3	Product (leaf)	323	Specific SKU / variant

IV. DATA PIPELINE

Figure 1 provides an overview of the four-stage training pipeline. Figure 2 shows a representative example of the detection task: densely packed shelf products that must be simultaneously localised and classified across four hierarchy levels.

A. Data Preparation

The NorgesGruppen dataset (NGD) provides 248 annotated retail shelf images across 323 fine-grained product categories in COCO format. Images are partitioned into an 80/20 train/validation split, converted to YOLO label format, and category IDs are remapped to L3 indices. Five-fold cross-validation splits are prepared for hyperparameter selection. Copy-paste augmentation ($p = 0.3$) is applied during fine-tuning to partially mitigate the low-data regime.

B. Phase 1: Domain Pre-Training on SKU-110K

Initialising from ImageNet weights places the backbone in a natural-image regime that differs substantially from densely packed retail shelves. YOLOv8x is therefore pre-trained on SKU-110K [1], a corpus of 11,000+ supermarket shelf images with $\approx 1.7M$ bounding box annotations across a single generic product class. Pre-training runs for 50 epochs at 1024×1024 resolution with mosaic augmentation ($p = 1.0$) and early stopping (patience 5), yielding a shelf-aware initialisation for all subsequent stages.

C. Phase 2: Hierarchical Fine-Tuning (hYOLO V4)

YOLOv8x is extended with a four-level hierarchical classification head. The principal architectural contribution over Tsenkova et al. [2] is *bidirectional cross-level information flow*: each level l receives the previous level’s prediction as context, and gradients propagate both upward and downward through the hierarchy. Per-level loss weights λ_l compensate for the gradient scaling introduced by this flow.

The total training loss is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{box}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{obj}} + \sum_{l=0}^3 \lambda_l \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}^{(l)} + \alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{consist}} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{BCE}}^{(l)}$ is binary cross-entropy with label smoothing ($\epsilon = 0.1$) and inverse-frequency positive weighting (capped at 10.0) for long-tail class balancing, and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{consist}}$ ($\alpha = 25$) penalises parent-child hierarchy violations.

Fine-tuning proceeds in two sub-phases: 50 frozen-backbone epochs training the classification head only, followed

by 250 epochs of full fine-tuning with gradual backbone unfreezing. Training uses AdamW with a cosine learning rate schedule; EMA weights are tracked and checkpoints are selected by hierarchical F1 on the validation fold.

D. Phase 3: HierSupCon Post-Training

To sharpen intra-brand discriminability, a HierSupCon contrastive post-training stage is applied (≈ 20 epochs). Lightweight projection heads are attached to the intermediate features at each hierarchy level. Sampling is hierarchy-aware:

- *Positives*: same L_l class.
- *Hard negatives*: same L_{l-1} parent, different L_l class (same brand, different SKU).
- *Easy negatives*: different L_{l-1} parent.

The backbone, detection head, and final classification layers are frozen; only the projection heads and hierarchical base convolutions receive gradients.

E. Phase 4: Prototype Calibration

A zero-shot prototype calibration step corrects frequency bias on rare classes by rebuilding the class prototype bank from training-set features without additional labelled data. This is especially relevant given that 1 of the 323 leaf classes has no training examples.

F. Inference

The final model (≈ 230 MB) is exported as a single-file ONNX graph (FP16, opset 18). The output tensor of shape $(1, N_{\text{anchors}}, 4 + 323)$ provides anchor-free bounding boxes and L3 leaf class scores; ancestor predictions are recovered by traversing the taxonomy. The confidence threshold and per-image detection cap are selected by sweeping $\text{conf} \in \{0.50, 0.65, 0.80\}$ and $\text{max_det} \in \{30, 50, 80\}$ on the validation fold.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

All training was conducted on an NVIDIA A100. Competition evaluation uses a weighted composite score:

$$\text{Score} = 0.70 \times \text{mAP}_{\text{det}} + 0.30 \times \text{mAP}_{\text{cls}} \quad (2)$$

evaluated on a held-out test set not available during training. Per-level classification accuracy and hierarchical F1 (F1Hier; [4]), which awards partial credit for correct ancestor predictions, are additionally reported on the internal validation split.

B. Results

Table II reports competition and validation performance.

The competition score of 82.4 is particularly notable given the dataset scale: 248 training images is an extremely low-data regime for 323-class fine-grained detection. The accuracy gradient across hierarchy levels, from 97.2% at L0 down to 88.4% at L3, confirms that the hierarchical head captures increasing difficulty at finer granularities, and that coarse-level structure is reliably preserved even when leaf-level identity is ambiguous.

Fig. 1. Overview of the four-stage training pipeline.

C. Analysis

The gap between internal F1Hier (0.9426) and competition detection mAP (0.63) reflects different evaluation protocols: F1Hier rewards partial credit for correct ancestor predictions, while competition mAP applies strict IoU-matched scoring on unseen imagery. The 88.4% L3 accuracy on the validation fold suggests that generalisation to unseen products and shelf configurations, rather than classification capacity, is the primary bottleneck, consistent with the limited training set of 248 images.

D. Strengths

The hierarchical head provides a meaningful inductive bias: even when the model fails at the leaf level, it tends to fail gracefully, predicting the correct brand or format rather than an unrelated section. This is precisely the behaviour F1Hier is designed to reward, and the strong L0–L2 accuracies (97.2%, 94.9%, 92.6%) confirm that coarse structure is well-learned even under data scarcity. The two-phase training schedule (frozen backbone followed by gradual unfreezing) mitigates the risk of catastrophic forgetting of the SKU-110K shelf pri-

Fig. 2. Example shelf image from the NorgesGruppen dataset, illustrating the dense detection and classification task. Image courtesy of NorgesGruppen / NM i AI 2026 [7].

TABLE II
COMPETITION AND VALIDATION RESULTS FOR hYOLO V4.

Metric	Value
Competition weighted score	82.4
Detection mAP (test)	63.0
F1Hier (val)	0.9426
L0 accuracy, section (val)	97.2%
L1 accuracy, format (val)	94.9%
L2 accuracy, brand (val)	92.6%
L3 accuracy, SKU (val)	88.4%

ors, which would otherwise be a significant concern when fine-tuning on fewer than 300 images. The bidirectional gradient flow between hierarchy levels also allows higher-level context (e.g., section identity) to inform lower-level predictions, a design choice that flat detectors cannot exploit.

E. Limitations

The primary limitation is data volume. With 248 training images and 323 leaf classes, one class has zero training examples and many others are represented by only a handful of instances. Under this regime, HierSupCon post-training provides limited benefit: the contrastive objective requires sufficient within-class variation to learn meaningful margins, and the prototype calibration step can only partially compensate for absent or near-absent classes. The mAP of 0.63 on unseen data further suggests that bounding box localisation, not classification, degrades most under distribution shift; unfamiliar shelf configurations, lighting conditions, and product facings expose the limits of a backbone pre-trained on SKU-110K generic shelves rather than Norwegian grocery retail specifically.

F. Future Work

Several directions would likely yield the largest gains. First, data augmentation targeted at localisation, including

MixUp, Mosaic, and more aggressive copy-paste, would improve bounding box robustness without requiring additional labelled images. Second, a larger labelled dataset remains the clearest path to closing the generalisation gap; even doubling to 500 images would meaningfully improve rare-class coverage and make HierSupCon more effective. Third, replacing the manually specified hierarchy with a learned or embedding-derived taxonomy could reduce sensitivity to taxonomy design decisions. Finally, test-time augmentation (TTA) with Weighted Box Fusion (WBF) ensemble decoding was not fully exploited under competition time constraints and would likely improve mAP on unseen imagery at inference time.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented hYOLO V4, a four-stage pipeline for hierarchical grocery product detection that achieves a competition weighted score of 82.4 on the NorgesGruppen dataset from just 248 training images. The key contributions are a bidirectional hierarchical classification head, a parent-consistency training objective, and HierSupCon contrastive post-training with hierarchy-aware sampling. The accuracy gradient from L0 (97.2%) to L3 (88.4%) demonstrates that the hierarchy provides a meaningful inductive bias even in severely data-limited settings. Future work includes applying the pipeline to larger retail datasets and exploring prototype-based few-shot extensions for novel SKU categories. The code and model weights are publicly available at [8] and [9] respectively.

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